

“MAGISTRLAR” CERTIFICATE OF AWARD

We hereby present this certificate to

Yulduz Mamadaminova

THE PROBLEMS IN PSYCHOLOGY

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANDI

